

ON THE VIBRATION CHARACTERISTICS OF INTERLAMINATED

HYBRID COMPOSITE PLATES

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Summary

Hybrid and metal-matrix composites have been proposed as a design alternative to reduce the effects due to transverse shear deformations. Here, nonlinear governing equations, including the effects of transverse shear deformation and rotatory inertia, for free vibrations of interlaminated hybrid plates are presented. The governing equations are in terms of a force function and transverse displacement. Using Galerkin technique and principle of harmonic balance approximate solution to governing equations is formulated for a rectangular plate with edges clamped against transverse displacement and free from in plane forces. Numerical results for the ratio of nonlinear fundamental frequency to linear frequency of different interlaminated hybrid plates are presented. The effects of hybridization and of transverse shear deformations and rotatory inertia on the frequency-amplitude response is discussed.

Introduction

In recent years advanced fiber reinforced composite materials have been widely used in fields such as aerospace technology, aircraft industry and various other industrial fields. However, due to their low shear moduli relative to in-plane elastic moduli, such composite material structures exhibit more pronounced effects due to transverse shear forces and rotatory inertia [1,2]. Hybrid and metal-matrix composites have been proposed as a viable material design alternatives to reduce the above effects. During the past two decades significant progress has been made in developing hybrid composites. They have already been used in many industries and new uses are being continually reported in technical and trade literature. Hybrid composite materials have been considered as high potential material in many fields since, they provide designers with the new freedom of tailoring composites to obtain superior performance than the conventional composites. Some of the advantages of hybrid are cost savings, inherent structural damping, higher fatigue strength, high impact resistance, non-catastrophic crack growth and failure characteristics. The flexibility in the choice and disposition of reinforcements in hybrid composites, however, leads to different possibilities of construction that it will not be easy to classify them. However, in a broad sense they can be divided into two groups, Dispersed Fibre Hybrids where, two or more types of fibre dispersed in a common resin matrix, Interlaminated Hybrids where, composite structure is made by bonding together two or more types of fibre ply and, if used, Core material. Each layer of interlaminated hybrids is of the same material and may be unidirectional or angled and the thickness of each layer is not necessarily the same. Due to the generality of construction, to be able to use a hybrid composite with ease and confidence requires a knowledge of the mechanical, thermal and failure properties for each specific hybrid arrangement. In the present paper, a procedure is presented to predict the nonlinear free vibration characteristics of interlaminated rectangular hybrid composite plates including the effects of transverse shear deformations and rotatory inertia. The analysis is general and can be used to study the nonlinear behaviour of laminates which are not symmetrical about a centre plane or symmetrical as well.

Governing Equations

In order to account for the effects of transverse shear deformation, rotatory inertia and midplane stretching, the displacement field in an interlaminated hybrid composite plate can be assumed to be of the form [3]:

$$\begin{aligned}U(x,y,z,t) &= u(x,y,t) + z\alpha(x,y,t) \\V(x,y,z,t) &= v(x,y,t) + z\beta(x,y,t) \\W(x,y,z,t) &= w(x,y,t)\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

In the above $u(x,y,t)$ and $v(x,y,t)$ are displacements of the laminate midplane in x and y coordinate directions. $w(x,y,t)$ is the laminate out-of-plane deflection, α, β are the effective rotational displacements of xz and yz planes. Here, t is the time and U, V, W are the displacements in x, y, z directions respectively. Using the geometric nonlinear strain-displacement relations, the Lagrangian strain components become,

$$\begin{aligned}\epsilon_x &= \epsilon_x^0 + z\alpha_{,x} & \epsilon_y &= \epsilon_y^0 + z\beta_{,y} \\ \epsilon_{xy} &= \epsilon_{xy}^0 + z(\alpha_{,y} + \beta_{,x}) & \epsilon_z &= 0 \\ \epsilon_{xz} &= \alpha + w_{,x} & \epsilon_{yz} &= \beta + w_{,y}\end{aligned}\tag{2}$$

where,

$$\epsilon_x^0 = u_{,x} + \frac{1}{2} w_{,x}^2; \epsilon_y^0 = v_{,y} + \frac{1}{2} w_{,y}^2; \epsilon_{xy}^0 = u_{,y} + v_{,x} + w_{,x}w_{,y}$$

Neglecting stress and strain normal to midplane the Kirchhoff stress - Lagrangian strain relations (Hooke's Law) for the n-th layer with respect to the x,y,z rectangular coordinate system are given by

$$[\sigma_{ij}^{(n)}] = [k_{ij}^{(n)}][\varepsilon_{ij}^{(n)}] \quad (3)$$

in which $[\varepsilon_{ij}^{(n)}]^T = [\varepsilon_x, \varepsilon_y, \varepsilon_{xy}, \varepsilon_{xz}, \varepsilon_{yz}]$ and $k_{ij}^{(n)}$ are the stiffness coefficients of the n-th layer in plate coordinates. If the n-th layer is not isotropic and the orientation of orthotropic axis is angled with respect to plate axis, then to obtain $k_{ij}^{(n)}$ a classical stiffness transformation is necessary [4].

Assuming each layer to be of constant thickness and existence of at least one plane elastic symmetry parallel to the plane of each layer, and considering a laminate of constant total thickness 'h', the following relations are obtained, for stress and couple resultants

$$\begin{Bmatrix} [N] \\ [M] \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} [A] & [B] \\ [B] & [D] \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} [\varepsilon^0] \\ [\kappa] \end{Bmatrix}, \quad \begin{Bmatrix} Q_x \\ Q_y \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} E_{11} & E_{12} \\ E_{12} & E_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \alpha + w_{,x} \\ \beta + w_{,y} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where,

N, Q, M are the stress and couple resultants defined as in the classical plate theory by

$$N_{ij} = \int_{-h/2}^{+h/2} \sigma_{ij}^{(n)} dz, \quad Q_i = \int_{-h/2}^{+h/2} \sigma_{iz}^{(n)} dz, \quad M_{ij} = \int_{-h/2}^{+h/2} \sigma_{ij}^{(n)} z dz, \quad (i, j = x, y) \quad (5)$$

In these matrices above

$$[N] = \begin{Bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad [M] = \begin{Bmatrix} M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad [\varepsilon^0] = \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^0 \\ \varepsilon_y^0 \\ \varepsilon_{xy}^0 \end{Bmatrix}, \quad [\kappa] = \begin{Bmatrix} \alpha_{,x} \\ \beta_{,y} \\ \alpha_{,y} + \beta_{,x} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

$$(A_{ij}, B_{ij}, D_{ij}) = \int_{-h/2}^{+h/2} k_{ij}^{(n)}(1, z, z^2) dz \quad (ij = 1, 2, 3),$$

$$E_{ij} = \int_{-h/2}^{+h/2} k_{(i+3)(j+3)}^{(n)} dz \quad (ij = 1, 2)$$

in which A_{ij} are the extensional stiffnesses, B_{ij} are the bending stretching coupling, D_{ij} are the flexural stiffnesses and E_{ij} are the thickness-shear stiffnesses. Hybrid plates having layers arranged arbitrarily, hence unsymmetric with respect to midplane experience bending-stretching coupling. However, coupling stiffnesses B_{ij} will disappear when the laminate is symmetric about midplane.

In the absence of surface and body forces (free vibration) the system of laminate equations of motion is of the form

$$N_{x,x} + N_{xy,y} = \gamma u_{,tt} + \eta \alpha_{,tt} \quad (7)$$

$$N_{xy,x} + N_{y,y} = \gamma v_{,tt} + \eta \beta_{,tt} \quad (8)$$

$$(N_x w_{,x} + N_{xy} w_{,y})_{,x} + (N_{xy} w_{,x} + N_y w_{,y})_{,y} + Q_{x,x} + Q_{y,y} = \gamma w_{,tt} \quad (9)$$

$$M_{x,x} + M_{xy,y} - Q_x = \delta \alpha_{,tt} + \eta u_{,tt} \quad (10)$$

$$M_{xy,x} + M_{y,y} - Q_y = \delta \beta_{,tt} + \eta v_{,tt} \quad (11)$$

On the right sides of these equations γ , η and δ are given by

$$(\gamma, \eta, \delta) = \int_{-h/2}^{+h/2} \rho^{(n)}(1, z, z^2) dz \quad (12)$$

where $\rho^{(n)}$ is the mass density of n -th layer. The above equations of motion are derived using Hamilton's principle and the details of this procedure can be found in [5] or elsewhere.

Force Function Model Method of Solution

The governing equations presented in the previous section are valid for any interlaminated hybrid composite plate. Exact close-form solutions satisfying these equations cannot be, yet, obtained without invoking small-displacement assumptions. Reddy and Chao [6] have studied the nonlinear oscillations of laminated rectangular plates based on a finite element model. Also, harmonic time function have been used in their analysis, although, it is well known that the time function is not harmonic even in the case of free vibration. Here, a method of solution based on a force function model is presented. If the inplane inertia terms and coupling inertia terms are neglected, the governing equations (7) and (8) are automatically satisfied by a force function F where,

$$[N_x; N_y; N_{xy}] = [F_{,yy}; F_{,xx}; -F_{,xy}] \quad (13)$$

Using a partial inversion of equation (4) for M_x , M_y and M_{xy} in equations (9)-(11) and eliminating dependent variables α and β the first equation of transverse motion in terms of F and w is obtained as

$$I_1(w) - I_2(F) = I_3(w_{,xx} F_{,yy} + w_{,yy} F_{,xx} - 2w_{,xy} F_{,xy}) \quad (14)$$

The second equation is derived from the condition of compatibility

$$\varepsilon_{x,yy}^0 + \varepsilon_{y,xx}^0 - \varepsilon_{xy,xy}^0 = w_{,xy}^2 - w_{,xx} w_{,yy} \quad (15)$$

The equation (15) in terms of force function F and transverse displacement w is given by

$$I_4(F) + I_5(w) = I_3(w_{,xy}^2 - w_{,xx} w_{,yy}) \quad (16)$$

Equations (14) and (16) constitute a system of equations governing the large amplitude flexural vibration of interlaminated hybrid plates. The detail derivation of the governing equations and the operators I_1 to I_5 can be found in [5]. It is observed that, with appropriate simplifications these equations can be used to study the individual effects of transverse shear deformation and rotatory inertia on the vibration characteristics of interlaminated hybrid plates with appropriate boundary conditions.

Boundary Conditions

Consider an initially flat, rectangular, elastic plate of length 'a' in x -direction and width 'b' in the y -direction. Although the governing equations can be solved for any edge conditions, in this study all edges are clamped against transverse motion and free from in plane stress.

$$w = \alpha = \beta = F_{,yy} = F_{,xy} = 0 \quad \text{at } x = \pm a/2$$

$$w = \alpha = \beta = F_{,xx} = F_{,xy} = 0 \quad \text{at } y = \pm b/2$$

Figure 1. Geometry of a rectangular clamped plate.

The displacement w and the force function F satisfying the above mentioned boundary conditions may be written in a series form;

$$F = \sum_{p=1}^{\infty} \sum_{q=1}^{\infty} [\lambda_{pq} f(t) + \mu_{pq} f^2(t)] \left((-1)^{p+1} + \cos \frac{2p\pi x}{a} \right) \left((-1)^{q+1} + \cos \frac{2q\pi y}{b} \right) \quad (17)$$

$$W = \sum_{r=1}^{\infty} \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} h \frac{f(t)}{4} \left((-1)^{r+1} + \cos \frac{2r\pi x}{a} \right) \left((-1)^{s+1} + \cos \frac{2s\pi y}{b} \right) \quad (18)$$

in which $f(t)$ is a periodic function of time, λ_{pq} and μ_{pq} are constants to be determined later. In view of the complex nonlinear nature of governing equations (14) and (16), only approximate solutions are attempted here on the basis of one-term mode shape. The single-mode expansion for w avoids coupled nonlinear modal equations. Now introducing equations (17) for F and the first term of equation (18) for w in the governing equation (16) and using the orthogonality relations an infinite set of differential equations fourth order in $f(t)$ are obtained. However, this set can be truncated to any desired degree of accuracy by choosing proper values for p and q . For a given value of p and q this set gives the same number of equations in coefficients λ_{pq} and μ_{pq} . The Galerkin procedure is applied to the governing equation (14) in order to minimize the error produced by single-mode approximation. This results in a sixth order differential equation for periodic time function $f(t)$. A periodic function, however, can be represented by a convergent series of harmonic functions whose frequencies are integral multiples of a certain fundamental frequency ω . Hence, the periodic time function $f(t)$ is expanded into a Fourier cosine series as

$$f(t) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} C_k \cos k \omega t \quad (19)$$

Substituting the assumed solution (19) into the first set of differential equations and equating the coefficients of like terms, constants λ_{pq} and μ_{pq} for the k -th harmonic are obtained as,

$$\lambda_{pq}^k = \frac{Z_1^{pq} - R_1 k^2 \omega^2 Z_2^{pq}}{H_1^{pq} - R_1 k^2 \omega^2 H_2^{pq} + R_1 k^4 \omega^4 H_3^{pq}} \quad (20)$$

$$\mu_{pq}^k = \frac{Z_3^{pq} - R_1 k^2 \omega^2 Z_4^{pq} + R_1 k^4 \omega^4 Z_5^{pq}}{H_1^{pq} - R_1 k^2 \omega^2 H_2^{pq} + R_1 k^4 \omega^4 H_3^{pq}}$$

where, H and Z are constant coefficients given in [5] and R_1 is the tracing constant which represents the effect of rotatory inertia. Similarly the second differential equation can be reduced to a set of simultaneous algebraic equations for C_k as

$$J_1^k C_k + J_2^k \bar{C}_k + J_3^k \bar{\bar{C}}_k = 0 \quad k=0,1,2,3... \quad (21)$$

in which \bar{C}_k and $\bar{\bar{C}}_k$ contain quadratic and cubic terms of C_k respectively and are presented in [5]. Equations (21) can be solved for Fourier coefficients C_k by the Newton-Raphson method, for a given set of plate parameters and nonlinear fundamental frequency ω . Once the Fourier coefficients C_k , λ_{pq} and μ_{pq} are determined, the transverse displacement w and the force function F can be uniquely determined.

Results and Discussion

To illustrate the generality of the method of analysis, an eight-ply unsymmetric cross-ply (0°/90°/0°/...) plate ($a = b = 10h$) is analysed. As shown in Figure 2, Graphite fiber reinforced layers (CFRP) and Glass fiber reinforced layers (GFRP) have been used to form different hybrids. Type (A) - (E) are sandwich composites where, the core of the hybrid is of GFRP and the shell (outer ply) is of CFRP. Type (C1) is an alternate ply hybrid with 50% CRFP, therefore, similar to Type (C). The following values for elastic constants were used in the analysis:

CFRP:	$E_1/E_2 = 40,$	$G_{12}/E_2 = 0.5,$	$\nu_{12} = 0.25$
	$G_{14}/E_2 = 0.5,$	$G_{24}/E_2 = 0.33,$	$\rho/E_2 = 0.2 \times 10^{-10}$
GFRP:	$E_1/E_2 = 3,$	$G_{12}/E_2 = 0.5,$	$\nu_{12} = 0.25$
	$G_{14}/E_2 = 0.5,$	$G_{24}/E_2 = 0.33,$	$\rho/E_2 = 0.2 \times 10^{-10}$

The first six terms in the truncated time series (19) are considered in this study. However, an analysis on the effect of number of terms in the time series on the results indicates that the series converges rapidly. Figure 3 shows the effect of hybridisation on the nonlinear frequency of the plate. In the figures presented ω is the nonlinear fundamental frequency, ω_0 is the corresponding linear frequency of a classical plate, excluding the effects of transverse shear and rotatory inertia and w/h is the ratio of center amplitude of vibration to plate thickness. The fundamental linear frequency of 100% GFRP defined by $\Omega_g = \omega_0 b^2 (\rho/E_2 h^2)^{1/2}$ is 14.5222. The nondimensionalized center amplitude-frequency response of Hybrid types (A), (C) and (E) are shown in Figure 4. In both figures 3 and 4 the relationships including the effects of transverse shear ($R_s = 1$) and rotatory inertia are added for comparison. From the above analysis the following observations can be made.

As expected the effects of transverse shear and rotatory inertia are quite significant, especially in thick plates. In this case ($a = 10h$), these effects are increased due to hybridisation. The frequency reduction due to these effects in Type (A) is approximately 3% at infinitesimally small amplitudes, while the frequency reduction in Type (E) is almost 20%. The plate shows a hardening type of nonlinearity for all types of hybridization and the effects due to transverse shear and rotatory inertia reduces at higher amplitude of vibration. The core-shell type hybrids show significant increase in vibration characteristics relative to alternate ply hybrids, (Type (C1)). Comparing the responses of Type (C) and Type (C1), both having 50% CFRP, Type (C) almost, exhibits the same vibration characteristics of a 100% CFRP hybrid, while the effects due to transverse shear and rotatory inertia are reduced by approximately 3%.

Figure 2 Types of Hybrids.

Figure 3. Effect of Hybridisation on the nonlinear frequency of unsymmetrically laminated eight-ply Hybrid cross-ply square clamped plate. ($a = 10h$)

Figure 4. Relation between frequency ratio and nondimensionalized center amplitude.

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